

Recommended citation: Brook, A. S. J. (2019). Diversifying indigenous narratives in design education: A decolonising design critique of affordance-based design. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 164-175). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14656142.

Diversifying Epistemological Narratives in Design Discourse Proposed Storying Methods on Place, People, and Affordances in Bali

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Conference Key Areas:

Diversity in Engineering Education; Gender, Inclusion and Ethics

Keywords:

Affordance, Stories, Shared Knowledge, Discourse

ABSTRACT

This paper frames the theory behind a longitudinal study and live action research approach, intending to be conducted with academic students and craftspeople in Bali, Indonesia. This study will take place through a de-centralised and de-institutionalised platform, co-created by myself and members of the West Balinese community, who aim to iteratively construct a Learning Centre with students and craftspeople.

This collaborative construction project will establish a socially interdependent knowledge system between students, craftspeople, and wider community- within which, stories of culture, society and place are created through designerly discourse and the 'act of doing' ^{[1][2][3]}. The physical architectural construction will become a signifier of these stories- detailing method, theory and onto-epistemological meaning, translated into legitimate sources of knowledge and data production ^{[1][4]}.

It is hoped that the Learning Centre construction will signify a 'true' and 'real' narrative of Balinese culture, society and place. By including more voices and 'ways of knowing' in the construction and knowledge production process, we hope that students and craftspeople will benefit from a diversification of onto-epistemological meanings, practices, and ways of thinking within both academia, craft, and the wider community^[5].

This aim is formed in response to the Eurocentric capitalist modernity that has been assimilated into Balinese institutions, and the touristic commodification of Balinese craft ^{[7][15]}.

By exemplifying the relational qualities of Affordance-Based Design (ABD), Decolonising Design (DD), and 'Respectful Design' ideology, this paper aims to outline how affordances within an architectural structure can signify stories of culture, society and place, co-produced as new knowledge.

1 INTRODUCING THE METHOD

1.1 Engagement with Being, Knowing, and Doing

This paper works towards an onto-ethico-epistemological research method for application in rural West Bali, between international and local students of design, architecture, or engineering, and situated Balinese craftspeople. A de-centralised and de-institutionalised platform has been co-created between myself, fellow research peers and these local communities in Bali. This platform has active partnerships with Balinese universities and educational organisations. This platform also has active involvement with community organisations within West Bali. It is the intent of this platform to engage students from these universities with craftspeople from West Balinese communities in designerly discourse and 1:1 scale construction of a Learning Centre, through which activity the onto-ethico-epistemological research will take place.

Being

Ontologically, this method recognises that we practice the design of ourselves- we design our world, while our world acts back on us and designs us back ^{[6][7][8]}. More specifically, this study explores a non-formalised process that models an ontological design loop- in which the student and Balinese craft communities participate in the design of themselves ^{[6][7]}. This would be captured through the co-production of stories related to culture, society and place, which are signified through the physical construction of a Learning Centre.

The student community in Bali could consist of students who; may be of Balinese origin studying within Balinese universities; or may be international students participating in Semester Abroad or Summer School programmes conducted by a third party. The Balinese craft community could consist of craftspeople who; may have completed formal education or higher education; may have learnt a skill or trade through vocation; may not be of Balinese origin; may be of all ages; may be multi-generational or 1st generation craftspeople; and may work with traditional, contemporary, or mixed methods. Ethically, this method sets out to perceive moral-ethical tensions within the current designerly discourse in Bali between these two groups, and establish intentionality to develop iterative interventions through open participation ^{[8][10][11]}.

Knowing

Epistemologically, this method hopes to share designerly 'ways of knowing' and 'doing' between academic students and Balinese craftspeople, through an iterative process of designerly discourse and 1:1 scale construction. This physical architectural artefact, and its affordances, will signify stories of both Balinese and non-Balinese culture, society, and place, and co-produce new knowledge related to the social, structural and material properties of place. An affordance is the provision of something from one system to another ^{[12][13]}. In this study, it is hoped that adaption of architectural affordances will signify new knowledge production through cultural, social and place-based reciprocity between students and craftspeople.

Doing

Practically, assessing adaption of affordances within the physical architecture could be achieved through observing:

- If/how a newly shared methods and materiality are used within construction, and what narratives they convey about a peoples' culture, society and place.
- If/how the construction affords more sustainable futures, and less moral-ethical tensions, based on the sharing of cultural, social, and place-based narratives.

This brings into focus the relational reciprocity between students and craftspeople in the co-production of knowledge. Within this process, students and craftspeople are encouraged to understand and question their motivations and goals related to cultural upbringing, societal norms, and place-based biases- which may impact their 'ways of knowing' and their interpretations of the world. Research methods similar to photo-voice, cultural probes, user-created personas, and focus groups will be used to collect stories which, in their own right, are legitimate sources of knowledge and data.

These stories become embedded within the methods, skills, and techniques of architectural construction, and relate to the cultural, social, or place-based provisions of the physical form. Observing change in these provisions may suggest change in the diversity of onto-epistemological meanings, practices, and ways of thinking within the student and craft communities. The hypothesis rooted within this study is that a change in diversity will lead away from the Eurocentric capitalist modernity assimilated into Balinese institutions, and the touristic commodification of Balinese craft.

1.2 The Marriage of Two Worlds

In addressing the above topics, I must also locate myself with an understanding of my own motivations and goals. I am a white, anglo, male- with my own 'ways of knowing' associated with my cultural, social and place. As such, I approach my study in Bali with limited understanding of the indigenous communities in the region. I hold an undergraduate and postgraduate degree in Industrial Design, have industry experience within graphical marketing and branding, and study doctoral research within the field of Architecture. Therefore, my projection of certain academic ideologies onto rural West Bali must be recognised as bias and assumptive, and my motivations as a data collecting researcher must also be recognised. In doing this, I hope to open respectful and reciprocal dialogue with the local West Balinese communities.

Bali is small Hindu-Buddhist society that has been continually forced to seek its own identity within changing frames of reference ^[14]. The current era of capitalist modernity and globalisation has been catalysed by unsustainable tourism in Bali. This is changing indigenous values, traditional cultural meanings, and ways of thinking, that have been derived over centuries alongside indigenous design ^{[7][15]}. As the Balinese begin to adopt western terms of economic productivity, supply and demand, and commodification of culture, so too do they adopt Eurocentric capitalist design within the island's popular culture and academic institutions ^{[7][15][16]}. Such a drastic transformation is causing population resettlement in both urban and rural areas-creating threats of economic and physical insecurity, and eroding cultural traditions ^{[15][17]}.

However, there is a growing movement in Bali working against these symptoms, highlighting the harmful effects of tourism in the region, and sharing the entrepreneurial voices of rural, indigenous Bali through 'sustainable tourism'. Sustainable tourism gives back to rural areas through economic opportunities, support of cultural craft, and community projects. My collaboration with this movement in Bali aims to both; revitalise and transform rural communities in Bali through youth and community empowerment initiatives; and, help diversify architectural education and profession through shared experiential activities, culminating in the 1:1 scale construction of a Learning Centre. The construction of the Learning Centre will connect students and academic institutions, both in Bali and worldwide, with local craftspeople.

The Learning Centre itself will provide educational classes to Balinese youth, and economic opportunities for Balinese entrepreneurs through ‘sustainable tourism’ initiatives.

1.3 Tying the Relational Knot

By examining the relational reciprocity between students, craftspeople, and the architectural artefact, it is possible to outline how affordances can signify stories of culture, society and place, and describe how affordances can be used to map any change in the onto-epistemological meanings, practices and ways of thinking. This can be expressed by exemplifying the relational qualities of Affordance-Based Design (ABD), Decolonising Design (DD), and ‘Respectful Design’ ideology.

Affordance-Based Design

ABD documents the relational system between Designer, Artefact, User, and other external stakeholders, within the design process ^{[12][18]}. Rather than focusing upon function (input > transformation > output), ABD focuses on performance by documenting what affordances are provided between Artefact-Artifact and Artefact-User, and what properties are selected between User-Designer and Designer-Artifact ^{[12][13]}.

Decolonising Design

DD is a process that questions who speaks within design discourse; challenging privileged, Euro-dominated academic institutions, and asking who produces knowledge and who benefits from that knowledge production ^{[16][19]}. DD focuses on the sustainable long term relations between artefacts and what they create in the world, rather than creating short term problem solving artefacts ^{[5][20]}.

‘Respectful Design’

‘Respectful Design’ is derived from Aboriginal Australian world views, and positions design in relation to systems of the natural world and the social world ^{[21][22]}. This is because design relates to everyone, in any geography, through our genetic ancestry and connection to ‘place’ ^{[22][23]}. ‘Respectful Design’ not only listens to human peers, but knowledge that is shared back by our environments- whether it be forests, seas, or corporate boardrooms ^[24]. This is not just an indigenous spiritual belief, but science ^{[23][25]}.

These various ideologies can help us address the relational qualities between the different stakeholders in the design discourse and construction process in Bali, and ponder more generally on the questions, “who designs, and why?”.

2 DESIGNER, ARTEFACT, AND USER

2.1 Who Designs?

In short, we all design *communally*. Our actions are bound, more or less, in our sense of place and our ancestry, and how they influence the ways we ‘know’ and ‘do’. Our sense of place comes not only from our geography, but from the knowledge that our environment shares back with us. These environments can be anything from; the home, the tundra, the school, the mountains, the church, the woodland, the laboratory, the workplace, the campfire etc ^[24]. Design can be practised by listening and responding to these environments, and the knowledge that they share ^[26]. Different ways we can receive knowledge from these environments include:

- ‘Authority’, such as education, upbringing, or media, that are trusted based on their source. This type of information can be bias, superficial and/ or privileged [16][19].
- ‘Experience’, such as personal action, inferring applied information that is discovered through time repeated experiences.
- ‘Tradition’, such as ancestral action, that is adopted based on previous application. Traditions have both excused our own violence through a sociological mechanism of myths, rituals, taboo and prohibitions [27], and formed age-old, common, and beneficial practices which respect valid, rigorous, academically sound, and useful indigenous knowledge [24][28].
- ‘Revelation’, such as a knowledge from a spiritual entity, that is believed out of faith. This can illustrate just how different the worlds are that we live in, depending on which revelation we accept or reject outright [29].
- ‘Logic’, such as causal effect, inferring philosophical plausibility (If A, then B). Correlation, however, does not always mean causation (B does not always mean A).
- ‘Science’, such as a controlled experiment, that has not been disproved. This experiences things in a methodical, conscious ways that allows us to make reasonable contrasts to other kinds of phenomena [29].

These different ‘ways of knowing’ have developed as a co-evolution between our genetic influences and cultural environment [25][30]. This is categorised as gene-culture interaction, or ‘gene-culture coevolution’ [31][32]. Our genes have a causal effect, through the neurological structure of our brains, on two major influences outside of our body:

1. They ‘select’ external properties in the environments outside of our body, that they interpret as beneficial to longevity and wellbeing [25][33]. In this respect, designing is fundamental to being human, as to design is to; interpret and interact with the social, structural and material properties of our environment, which prefigures our actions [6].
2. From birth, we neurologically mirror the needs, desires, and actions of others. This means that our own ‘self’- our meanings, feelings, and thoughts- are formed in relation to others. This occurs by interpreting and imitating their intentions- their interactions, responses and behaviours- as a determining factor in our own actions [27][34][35]. This can be defined as a communal reciprocity or collective unconsciousness, such as academic, societal, cultural or religious beliefs

Therefore, many individuals can communally act together in the design of themselves through a connection to place, environment, and the other [9]. In this process, ‘user’ becomes synonymous with ‘designer’, as we are both the designers and users of an environment formed through a collective unconsciousness with others. Through relational research and design methods, the focus can become that of a *conscious* interdependence between individual, collective, and environment [7][36]. The reciprocity between the individual students and craftspeople in Bali, and their collective community, attribute meaning to the architectural artefact they create- as they are all both physically invested in its creation, and psychologically invested in its use. [37][38]

2.2 And Why?

Why, and how, we design is dictated by our collective ‘ways of knowing’. The wider Balinese community can be seen to practice the design of themselves in an ongoing

self-creation ^{[6][7][8]} that stems from their collective ‘ways of knowing’; authority (indigenous schooling and community upbringing), tradition (caste system, non-capitalist and cooperative ideals), revelation (Buddhist spirituality and Hindu beliefs) and logic (causal effects of unsustainable westernised modernity in the region). The craftspeople of West Bali may, or may not, be consciously aware of their interdependence with the larger unconscious collective of the Balinese community. Yet, their motivations for ‘why’ and ‘how’ they design is influenced by a collective intent bound up in culture, society and place.

The same is true for the collaborating international and local Balinese students, whose design motivations are influenced by collective intent bound up in their respective culture, society and place.

Similarly, the same is true for the motivations behind my own involvement, and that of the community led organisations I am engaged with. My own motivations as a researcher and a designer, taken in isolation, affect my interpretations of the broader collective work being carried out by the communities of West Bali. In reflection of the wider motivations to *revitalise* communities through *youth empowerment*, and *help* students and professionals through a *change* in *cultural and social* settings, I must address the possibility of this project being labelled as ‘Design for Social Good’.

‘Design for Social Good’ has been critiqued as a method for privileged middle class individuals who wish to help others through ‘quick fix’ solutions ^{[19][20]}, implementing ‘Selfish Altruism’ or a ‘Potlatch’ style of altruistic donation. This states that, whilst we give to others, we also exact power, esteem, and social status in return in an act of superiority and dominance; “I can afford to make a donation to you” ^{[25][39]}. However, this research project focuses upon the motivations behind the student and Balinese craft communities’ design of itself, aiming to give research and design power to the Balinese people, and to initiate a respectful and reciprocal sharing of knowledge.

Research methods similar to photo-voice, cultural probes, user-created personas, and focus groups will be used to share stories between the students and craftspeople in an attempt to understand their motivations. These methods will use a variety of playful triggers- tangible or non-tangible objects and mediums ^[40] - to express the interpretations, meanings, and motivations behind the social, structural and material properties of the architectural form. Both the architectural form, and these tangible/intangible objects, are signifiers of stories which interpret onto-epistemological meanings, practices, and ways of thinking within the student and craft communities. It is hypothesised that:

1. Interactions between students and craftspeople will diversify their ‘ways of knowing’ through relational reciprocity of cultural, societal and place-based stories.
2. This will elicit new interpretations and behaviours through exposure to new environments, authorities, traditions, revelations, logics etc.
3. New interpretations will cause a change in the collective cultural, societal and place-based stories between students and craftspeople.
4. Changes in these stories will be mapped through the affordances offered by both the final architectural form, and the tangible/intangible objects used within data collection.
5. It is hoped that any change in affordances will offer provision away from Eurocentric capitalist modernity, towards more sustainable futures for Balinese architectural education and craft.

3 “PRACTICE MAKES PERFECT”

3.1 Knowing by Doing

As Fry ^[2] interprets Heidegger ^[3], “what is known is lodged in the practical performative act, as it is expressed by the hand as exercised skill” (p.93), and knowledge is produced between the subjects and the architectural artefact through the act of doing ^[6]. It is the affordances of an architectural artefact that determine the act of doing ^[12], and therefore knowledge is signified between the subject and the architectural artefact through affordance. These affordances are dependant on the different ways that we ‘know’ and ‘do’, interpreted and imitated through the interactions, responses and behaviours elicited between us and our world. This creates a cyclical and iterative process of communal knowledge production through ‘doing’- where artefacts prototype our local world, and our local world prototypes artefact back ^{[5][6][7][41]}.

I hope to mirror this iterative prototyping process through a live action research cycle of planning, acting, observing, and reflecting. Students and craftspeople take action through designerly dialogue and iterative 1:1 scale construction. They may then observe and reflect on stories of culture, society, and place signified within this relational and reciprocal process. Through the use of research methods similar to photo-voice, cultural probes, user-created personas, and focus groups, it is hoped that students and craftspeople will be able to express their stories as legitimate sources of data and knowledge, shared through the communal act of doing.

4 CONCLUSION

Ontologically, this method acknowledges the cyclical and iterative process of communal self-design; that we practice design through our relation to place and to each other and, in turn, we are designed by our designing and by that which we have designed.

Ethically, this method recognises the moral-ethical tensions that currently exist within Balinese education and craft, and questions the motivations of external design discourse in West Bali. Through open participation in design discourse and 1:1 scale construction, it is hoped that shared ‘ways of knowing’ will engage students and craftspeople in an iterative cycle of thought and practice. This will hopefully establish intentionally to develop interventions that tackle these moral-ethical tensions.

Epistemologically, this method looks at the relation between knowledge, culture, society and place, as expressed through stories signified within the social, structural and material properties of architectural form. The relations between these subjects offers new opportunities for diverse knowledge production, from which we draw on different interpretations of our world and what it affords us.

This provides a platform for the suggested onto-ethico-epistemological method that, practically, hopes to induce a change in diversity that will lead away from the Eurocentric capitalist modernity, towards more sustainable futures for Balinese architectural education and craft.

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